

Supplementary Table 4. Results of the Brown-Forsythe test for homogeneity of variance among different groups for miR-326, miR-20a, and miR-128.

mRNA	<i>B-F</i>	<i>p</i>
hsamiR326	9.12	0.005
hsamiR20a 5p	9.12	0.005
HsamR128 3p	11.5	0.002

miR – microRNA ***B-F***– Brown-Forsythe test value; ***df*** – number of freedom – ***df***=1; ***p*** – level of statistical significance